

Infrared Thermal Imaging for Automotive HCI: A Systematic Review and Exploratory Meta-Analysis

Abstract

Thermal imaging offers a promising non-invasive and real-time method for assessing cognitive load by monitoring facial temperature changes. In this paper, we explore the potential application of this technology in the automotive sector. To this end, we present a systematic literature review and meta-analysis aimed at evaluating the effectiveness of infrared thermal imaging in driving simulators. Through a thorough keyword search, we selected 13 studies from an initial pool of 5204 unique records for in-depth analysis. Specifically, our review focused on three key areas: Thermal Imaging Application, Data Capture, and Image Data Processing. In addition, we conducted an exploratory meta-analysis on four studies (15 data points), which suggests that thermal cameras may be sensitive to cognitive load changes in driving simulators but also highlights substantial heterogeneity and reporting limitations in the current evidence base.

Keywords: Automotive, Human-Computer Interaction, Thermal Imaging, Cognitive Load, Driving Simulator, Literature Review, Meta-Analysis

1. Introduction

Mental workload constitutes a central construct in ergonomics and human factors engineering, with direct implications for system design, human reliability, and operator safety (Young et al., 2015; Wickens, 2008). Within the automotive domain, understanding the cognitive demands imposed on drivers is essential for designing interfaces that support, rather than compromise, safe vehicle operation (De Waard, 1996). However, as Young et al. (2015) observe in their comprehensive review, mental workload remains a construct characterized by definitional heterogeneity and operationalization inconsistencies, complicating both measurement and cross-study comparison.

Following the terminological framework established by ISO 10075-1 (2017), it is necessary to distinguish between three related but distinct constructs: mental load refers to the objective task demands placed on an operator; mental strain denotes the psychophysiological response to those demands within an individual; and mental workload represents the subjective interaction between external demands and internal resources (Hart and Staveland, 1988; De Waard, 1996). This tripartite distinction carries significant methodological implications. Self-report instruments such as the NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX) (Hart and Staveland, 1988), the Subjective Workload Assessment Technique (Reid and Nygren, 1988), and the Rating Scale Mental Effort (Zijlstra, 1995) primarily capture the subjective workload experience. Performance metrics index the behavioral consequences of load-resource interactions. Physiological measures, by contrast, provide indices of mental strain—the organism’s response to imposed demands—rather than direct measures of load itself.

This distinction is consequential for interpreting physiological data in ergonomic contexts. The well-documented dissociation between subjective workload and task performance (Vidulich and Wickens, 1986) suggests that workload is not a unitary construct but rather a multidimensional phenomenon involving effort,

frustration, temporal pressure, and performance decrements that may vary independently (Hart and Staveland, 1988). Wickens' Multiple Resource Theory (Wickens, 2002, 2008) further specifies that cognitive resources are not fungible: demands on visual-spatial processing, verbal-linguistic processing, and response execution draw on separable pools, such that workload effects depend critically on the alignment between task demands and available resources. Any physiological measure intended to index workload must therefore be interpreted with reference to which component or components of this multidimensional space it captures.

Traditional physiological approaches to workload assessment—Electrocardiogram (ECG), Galvanic Skin Response (GSR), Electroencephalography (EEG), and pupillometry—have demonstrated sensitivity to cognitive demand manipulations but require physical attachment of sensors to the operator (Lohani et al., 2019). In automotive research contexts, contact-based instrumentation introduces practical constraints: sensor placement may restrict movement, affect naturalistic behavior, and prove impractical for continuous in-vehicle monitoring outside controlled laboratory settings (Santos et al., 2025). These limitations have motivated interest in contactless sensing modalities capable of capturing physiological indices without physical encumbrance.

Infrared thermal imaging has emerged as a candidate technology for non-invasive physiological monitoring in human factors applications (Gade and Moeslund, 2014). Thermal cameras detect electromagnetic radiation in the mid-wave (3 μm to 5 μm) or long-wave (8 μm to 14 μm) infrared spectrum, producing spatially resolved maps of surface temperature. Because human skin approximates black-body radiation characteristics within this spectral range (Hardy et al., 1934), thermal imaging enables remote measurement of facial temperature distributions with high spatial and temporal resolution.

The physiological basis for using facial thermography as an index of mental strain lies in autonomic nervous system regulation of peripheral blood flow. Sympathetic activation—characteristic of stress, arousal, and effortful cognitive processing—triggers peripheral vasoconstriction, reducing blood flow to the skin surface and producing measurable temperature decreases in specific facial regions (Engert et al., 2014; Ioannou et al., 2014). The nasal region, richly innervated by sympathetic fibers and characterized by superficial vasculature with minimal subcutaneous tissue, has proven particularly sensitive to sympathetically mediated temperature changes (Or and Duffy, 2007; Shastri et al., 2012). The forehead region, by contrast, exhibits greater thermal stability due to its distinct vascular architecture, providing a potential reference for computing differential indices.

Critically, the thermophysiological response captured by facial imaging reflects sympathetic arousal, a component of mental strain, rather than cognitive workload per se. This distinction is not merely semantic. Sympathetic activation may arise from cognitive effort, emotional stress, physical exertion, or thermoregulatory demands, each with different implications for driver state inference and system design. The observed correlation between facial temperature changes and subjective workload reports (Or and Duffy, 2007) demonstrates convergent validity but does not establish that thermal imaging measures workload in its full multidimensional sense. Rather, thermography appears to index the autonomic arousal component of the strain response, which may or may not correspond to task-specific cognitive demands depending on experimental context.

This epistemological positioning has direct implications for applied ergonomics. If thermal imaging primarily captures sympathetic arousal, its utility for driver monitoring systems depends on: (a) the extent to which arousal covaries with safety-relevant performance decrements in specific driving contexts; (b) the temporal dynamics of the thermal response relative to the timescales of adaptive intervention; and (c) the discriminability of cognitively-induced arousal from other sources of sympathetic activation (thermal

65 environment, emotional state, physical activity). These questions remain incompletely resolved in the existing literature.

In this article, we present a systematic literature review and exploratory meta-analysis examining the application of infrared thermal imaging for driver state assessment in simulator environments. We deliberately constrain our scope to automotive and piloting simulator studies to ensure methodological comparability across contexts in which thermal imaging has been deployed for workload-related assessment. Our objectives are threefold: first, to characterize the methodological landscape through a design space encompassing application contexts, data capture parameters, and signal processing approaches; second, to provide an exploratory quantitative synthesis of effect sizes reported in studies comparing thermal indices across workload conditions; and third, to identify the methodological heterogeneity and reporting gaps that currently limit confidence in synthesized findings.

We explicitly frame this meta-analysis as exploratory rather than confirmatory. Given the limited number of eligible studies, the heterogeneity in operationalization of both independent variables (workload manipulations) and dependent variables (thermal indices), and the detected publication bias in the available evidence, our quantitative synthesis should be interpreted as characterizing the current state of an emerging research domain rather than providing definitive population parameter estimates. The substantial residual variance observed across studies—only partially explained by methodological moderators—itself constitutes a finding, indicating that the field has not yet converged on standardized protocols or established which thermal indices most reliably track which components of mental strain.

2. Methodology

85 We performed the systematic literature review using the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) framework (Page et al., 2021), for which a summative illustration can be found in Figure 1. The search was conducted through a series of electronic databases: IEEE Xplore¹, SAGE², Springer³, and Elsevier⁴, using the keywords: *facial temperature*, *facial thermography*, *thermography*, *infrared camera*, *thermal camera*, and *thermal imaging*. After duplicates were removed, a total of 5204 articles were found. Upon downloading from each database a csv file, we parsed the titles and keywords applying the following terms: cognitive strain, cognitive load, cognitive workload (or work-load), mental strain, mental load, mental workload (or work-load). We used the keyword variants of driving (e.g., driv*, driv* behavior) to further constrain the research. Toward this end, 54 articles were retrieved for screening, and 13 papers were selected for in-depth review (Table 1). These papers were selected based on the criteria for using a driving or piloting simulator and utilizing an infrared thermal imaging camera.

Subsequently, we conducted an exploratory meta-analysis of the collected records to obtain a quantitative summary of the reported effects when using thermal imaging to measure cognitive load in driving simulators and to diagnose sources of variability across studies, rather than to derive a definitive estimate of overall effectiveness. We frame this analysis as exploratory given the small number of eligible studies and anticipated heterogeneity in methods and contexts. Eight studies lacked the primary data for the meta-analysis—i.e., did not report the necessary statistics needed to calculate the Standardized Mean Difference (SMD) and their

¹<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org>

²<https://journals.sagepub.com>

³<https://link.springer.com>

⁴<https://sciencedirect.com>

Figure 1: A summary illustration of the literature we collected following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) framework (Moher et al., 2009). Of 5204 unique records, 54 were retrieved for screening, 13 studies were analyzed in-depth, and four coded for the meta-analysis using the Population, Intervention, Comparison group, Outcomes, Time frame, Setting (PICOTS) framework (Riva et al., 2012). Unfortunately, eight studies lacked the necessary statistics needed for the meta-analysis.

Confidence Intervals (CI) (Lipsey and Wilson, 2001). Therefore, for the meta-analysis, four studies were coded using the PICOTS framework (Population, Intervention, Comparison group, Outcomes, Time frame, Setting) (Riva et al., 2012). However, because these studies included multiple experiments, we could extract 15 data points containing the SMD and CI for the meta-analysis.

2.1. Quality Assessment

We conducted a narrative quality assessment of included studies, evaluating methodological rigor across key domains relevant to psychophysiological measurement research. We adopted a qualitative rather than quantitative scoring approach for the following reasons. First, the methodological heterogeneity across studies—spanning diverse thermal imaging applications, ROI configurations, and processing pipelines—renders standardized scoring problematic. Instruments developed for clinical trials (Cochrane Risk of Bias) or observational epidemiology (Newcastle-Ottawa Scale) assume methodological comparability that does not obtain in this evidence base. Applying such instruments would require extensive adaptation that risks producing scores with unclear validity. Second, the small number of studies ($N = 13$ for qualitative synthesis, $k = 4$ for meta-analysis) precludes meaningful quality-weighted analyses or sensitivity analyses stratified by quality category. Numerical scores might imply a precision of quality differentiation that the evidence base cannot support. Third, consistent with the exploratory framing of this review, we prioritize transparent characterization of methodological variation over reductive quantification. A narrative approach permits nuanced assessment of domain-specific strengths and limitations that binary or ordinal scoring would obscure. The quality assessment is operationalized through the design space analysis presented in Section 3. The three dimensions—Application, Data Capture, and Data Processing—simultaneously organize the descriptive synthesis and expose methodological limitations: incomplete reporting of camera specifications, inconsistent ROI justification, absent environmental controls, and heterogeneous processing pipelines are identified as domain-specific quality concerns rather than abstracted into numerical scores. This integrated approach ensures that quality appraisal remains grounded in specific methodological features rather than aggregate ratings of unclear interpretability.

3. Design Space and Findings of the Literature Review

To organize the qualitative synthesis and structure cross-study comparison, we developed an analytical framework characterizing the methodological configuration of thermal imaging research in automotive contexts. This design space emerged inductively from comparative analysis of included studies and serves three functions within the review: organizing the descriptive synthesis, identifying methodological gaps and inconsistencies, and structuring the research agenda.

We emphasize that the design space constitutes an analytical tool rather than a validated predictive framework. Its utility lies in making explicit the methodological choices researchers face when implementing thermal imaging for workload assessment, not in predicting which configurations will yield optimal measurement performance. The latter question—which ROIs, processing pipelines, and application contexts produce the most valid and reliable workload indices—remains empirically unresolved and represents a primary target for future research that the design space helps to articulate.

The framework comprises three dimensions derived through iterative thematic analysis of methodological descriptions across all included studies:

Application. This domain describes the functional role of thermal imaging within a study: physiological measurement (using thermal indices as dependent variables in workload research), design validation (using thermal data to compare interface alternatives), real-time monitoring (implementing thermal-based state detection for adaptive systems), or auxiliary sensing (using thermal imaging for non-physiological purposes such as head pose estimation).

Data Capture. The dimension encompasses the measurement configuration: camera hardware (spectral range, sensitivity, refresh rate), regions of interest (anatomical targets and their physiological rationale), capture geometry (camera placement, field of view), and environmental conditions (ambient temperature control, acclimatization procedures).

Data Processing. Finally, data processing characterizes the signal extraction pipeline: ROI segmentation approach (manual delineation, model-based tracking, algorithmic detection), feature computation (absolute temperature, temperature differentials, derived indices such as perspiration energy), temporal processing (averaging windows, rate-of-change computation), and artifact handling.

These dimensions are orthogonal in principle—choices along one dimension do not logically constrain choices along others—though empirical co-occurrences exist in the current literature (e.g., perinasal ROI tends to co-occur with model-based segmentation and perspiration energy computation, reflecting the methodological approach of a specific research group).

3.1. Thermal Imaging Application

Several trends can be determined in thermal imaging in the literature we reviewed. Six research papers attempt to demonstrate the validity of using infrared thermal imaging as a tool to provide physiological measurements of a subject in a driving simulator (Anzengruber and Riener, 2012; Kajiwara, 2014; Murai et al., 2008; Zhang et al., 2019; Wesley et al., 2010; Altschaffel et al., 2014). Two papers use these measurements to validate an experimental setup or automotive design (Kim et al., 2011; Jeong et al., 2018). Two papers demonstrate the usage of infrared thermal imaging to determine moments of driver distraction or the high cognitive workload of a driver in real-time (Pavlidis et al., 2018; Panagopoulos and Pavlidis, 2019). One paper utilizes infrared thermal imaging to determine head position and orientation in the car (Wu et al., 2018). Finally, one additional paper proposes a theoretical method but not implementation details (Mitas and Ryguła, 2010).

Study	N	Age		Gender	
		Mean	SD	Male	Female
Panagopoulos and Pavlidis (2019) ^a	59	n/a	n/a	26	33
Pavlidis et al. (2018) ^b	47	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Or and Duffy (2007), Experiment I ^c	16	24.2	4.9	16	17
	17	48.8	7.1	–	–
Or and Duffy (2007), Experiment II ^c	6	25.7	5.2	9	4
	7	46.7	6.4	–	–
Kim et al. (2011)	33	n/a	n/a	30	3
Zhang et al. (2019)	18	27.5	4.5	14	4
Jeong et al. (2018)	13	25.2	2.0	13	0
Wesley et al. (2010)	11	27.5	n/a	4	7
Anzengruber and Riener (2012)	9	n/a	n/a	9	0
Kajiwara (2014)	4	22.0	.71	4	0
Wu et al. (2018)	1	n/a	n/a	1	0
Murai et al. (2008)	1	n/a	n/a	1	0
Altschaffel et al. (2014)	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Mitas and Rygula (2010)	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a

Table 1: A detailed overview of the participants recruited in the reviewed literature. Note: some research papers have separated the participants into groups of age: *a*) two groups of ages: 18–27 and 60+, *b*) two groups of ages: 18–27 and 55+, gender-balanced, *c*) two groups of ages: 18–35 and 36–64.

170 3.1.1. Thermal Imaging as a Physiological Measurement Tool

In six articles we reviewed the attempt to develop methods of using infrared thermal imaging as a physiological measurement tool. In two experiments, Or and Duffy (2007) have shown that forehead temperature, in arousal states, tends to remain stable while the nose temperature decreases. In the first experiment, participants were asked to drive in a simulated environment and were exposed to a secondary task (mental arithmetic). The facial temperature was measured pre- and post-stimulus, and the Modified Cooper-Harper questionnaire was assessed. First, the authors found a correlation between nose and forehead temperature with the Modified Cooper-Harper questionnaire. Secondly, they observed that nose temperature decreased when the participant was occupied with the secondary task, while forehead temperature remained constant. The second experiment was conducted in real and simulated driving conditions. Similar results were found for the simulation, i.e., decreased nose temperature and constant forehead temperature. However, these results were not confirmed under the actual driving condition. Anzengruber and Riener (2012) show that their method is adequate to infer “mental conditions of the driver” but point out that the difference in states is very low (0.25 °C) and that other factors such as food intake, fatigue, and body position might have a more significant impact on body temperature, which limits the approach in real-world scenarios. Kajiwara (2014) shows that while the combination of physiological features captured is a valid measure of driver’s mental workload, noise and sunlight significantly inhibit the potential of this system to be implemented in real-world conditions. Murai et al. (2008) demonstrate that the difference between nasal and forehead temperatures is quicker to react to moments of the cognitive load than measurements of high-low-frequency heart rate analyses. Zhang et al. (2019) demonstrate that facial temperatures change in driving situations that require sudden and quick driver input (such as an unobserved vehicle swerving into the driver’s lane).

Finally, Wesley et al. (2010) show that the mean temperature in the supra-orbital signal is significantly higher when participants in a driving simulator have to fulfill distracting tasks, showing that infrared thermal imaging can be used to determine the driver’s distraction. In contrast, Altschaffel et al. (2014) find that temperature variations observed in their data sets are not statistically significant to determine stress or

cognitive load. Temperature differences occurred sporadically or with a significant delay between the increased workload demand and skin temperature reaction, showing that the method utilized was inadequate as a workload measure. Since the reason is not immediately evident from the data provided, there could remain several unidentified factors that influence the efficiency of thermal imaging as a physiological measurement tool.

3.1.2. Thermal Imaging to Validate Experimental Setups or Designs

Both Jeong et al. (2018) and Kim et al. (2011) use infrared thermal imaging as a measurement to validate experimental setups. Jeong et al. (2018) utilize variations in participants' nasal temperature to argue that a vehicle control method utilizing joystick control produces less driver workload and "stress" than using a steering wheel to control a vehicle in identical driving conditions. Moreover, Kim et al. (2011) use their participants' skin temperature measurements to validate a proposed simulated highway design over another. Both of the stated papers find that their measurements are in-line with additional physiological measurements.

3.1.3. Thermal Imaging as a Real-time Measure of Driver Workload

In two research papers, the authors show that a real-time measurement of driver workload and driver distractions is feasible using an infrared thermal imaging camera (Pavlidis et al., 2018; Panagopoulos and Pavlidis, 2019). For instance, Pavlidis et al. (2018) use the measure of perinasal perspiration to activate a biofeedback sensor that alerts the driver of distracted driving using a self-starting Cumulative Sums algorithm that activates and deactivates a warning light when perspiration passes a threshold, notifying a driver of his distracted mental state. Further, Panagopoulos and Pavlidis (2019) show that perinasal perspiration combined with other physiological measurements can accurately predict distracted and aggressive driving moments in a data set from a distracted driving experiment.

3.1.4. Thermal Imaging to Determine the Driver's Head Position

The only paper Wu et al. (2018) that does not directly use infrared thermal imaging as a physiological measurement demonstrates that tracking the driver's head position in a cab using thermal infrared imaging is feasible in an unobtrusive manner. Thermal imaging was only used to identify facial landmarks to calculate head tilt and position. They also demonstrate minor pitch and yaw changes—ranging from one to two degrees—in the driver's head positions.

3.2. Thermal Imaging Data Capture

As using an infrared thermal imaging camera was one of the criteria for inclusion in the in-depth review, all of the papers analyzed use thermal imaging to capture subject data. Most of the research papers examined set their studies in simulators, except for Wu et al. (2018), who performed a study in a moving vehicle, and for Or and Duffy (2007), who conducted multiple studies in both natural and simulated environments. Other studies used a pre-captured dataset of drivers (Panagopoulos and Pavlidis, 2019) or described a theoretic experiment setup (Mitas and Ryguła, 2010). Specifications such as camera models, image sensitivity, and refresh rate are provided in Table 2.

3.2.1. Regions of Interest

Measuring the cognitive effort of a driver is achieved by measuring a change in face skin temperature (Gade and Moeslund, 2014). This is in line with the seminal paper by Or and Duffy (2007), which shows that

Study	Camera Model	Sensitivity	Refresh rate
Jeong et al. (2018)	FLIR A20	.1°C	30 Hz
Kim et al. (2011)	FLIR A20	.1°C	30 Hz
Or and Duffy (2007)	Mikron MicroScan 7200V	.08°C	n/a
Pavlidis et al. (2018)	FLIR Tau 640	.05°C	n/a
Anzengruber and Riener (2012)	FLIR SC655	.05°C	n/a
Wesley et al. (2010)	ThermoVision SC6000 MWIR	.01°C	n/a
Kajiwara (2014)	Vionics Air 32	n/a	10 Hz
Zhang et al. (2019)	Optris PI640	.075°C	n/a
Murai et al. (2008)	n/a	.1°C	n/a
Wu et al. (2018)	n/a	n/a	n/a
Altschaffel et al. (2014)	n/a	n/a	n/a
Panagopoulos and Pavlidis (2019)	Previously collected dataset	n/a	1 Hz
Mitas and Ryguła (2010)	Theoretic setup	n/a	n/a

Table 2: The table shows an overview of the thermal cameras used in the reviewed literature. Sensitivity is specified as the temperature difference where a change is indistinguishable from noise, the Noise Equivalent Temperature Difference (NETD).

235 forehead temperature does not change significantly between start and end of an experiment setup, but that the nasal temperature does, and that it decreases with the amount of cognitive effort used by the driver.

No age effects were observed, however; Or and Duffy (2007) observe that the cognitive effort is significantly lower when piloting an actual vehicle compared to driving in a simulator. Measuring nose tip and forehead temperature has been repeatedly utilized in the literature (Kajiwara, 2014; Jeong et al., 2018; 240 Murai et al., 2008; Zhang et al., 2019). In these studies, the nose tip and forehead region have been determined manually (Kajiwara, 2014; Jeong et al., 2018) or through spectacles of precise dimensions (Murai et al., 2008). Alternatively, a Histograms of Oriented Gradients (HOG) detector was trained on a set of manually labeled snapshots to detect the regions automatically (Zhang et al., 2019).

Additional Regions of Interest (RoI)s have been considered in other simulated studies. Wesley et al. (2010) 245 trace the area above the eye affected by the supraorbital nerve. The perinasal region, as defined by Shastri et al. (2012), which describes the area between the upper lip and the nose, is utilized by two studies (Panagopoulos and Pavlidis, 2019; Pavlidis et al., 2018). Further research, however, did not limit their data collection to a specific area of the face; instead, they recorded temperature values of the entire face (Altschaffel et al., 2014; Anzengruber and Riener, 2012; Wu et al., 2018). In contrast, Mitas and Ryguła (2010) suggest employing 250 infrared thermal imaging to measure Percentage Eye Openness Tracking, limiting their regions of interest to the eyes only. Figure 2 illustrates the identified RoIs.

3.2.2. The Capture of Further Physiological Data

In addition to capturing infrared thermal imaging data, papers obtained in our analysis record additional physiological data to confirm their findings or demonstrate the validity of their method. Jeong et al. (2018) 255 captured the Electrocardiogram (ECG), Electromyogram (EMG), Electrooculogram (EOG), and Galvanic Skin Response (GSR) of the study participants to demonstrate the correlation between other physiological measurements and data obtained through infrared thermal imaging. Zhang et al. (2019) collected ECG and GSR to correlate their findings. Kim et al. (2011) collected ECG, EMG, EOG, and GSR data in the same manner as Jeong et al. (2018). Murai et al. (2008) measured the heart rate of their participant to verify their 260 method of using thermal imaging. Panagopoulos and Pavlidis (2019) combined the thermal image readings of their data set with heart rate, breathing rate, and GSR readings to measure cognitive workload.

Figure 2: An overview of the Regions of Interest (RoI) we identified during the literature analysis. From left to right: (a) supraorbital, (b) forehead, (c) nose-tip, and (d) perinasal regions.

3.3. Thermal Imaging Data Processing

As with digital video cameras, thermal cameras are subject to noise and other image artifacts (Gade and Moeslund, 2014). Valuable temperature data, in this regard, can be obtained from image processing tools. Processing the image data and extracting temperature values is required to reproduce an experiment and verify the data obtained accurately. This subsection will detail the methodologies utilized to extract data in the reviewed literature. Kajiwara (2014) extracts monochrome square pixel values from the nose tip and forehead regions, averages the pixel density per frame per square, and subtracts the density of the forehead area from the nose area, obtaining the difference in temperature signals between the forehead and nose over time. This value is combined with other physiological features such as skin potential change and skin conductance over time to measure the driver's mental workload. Zhang et al. (2019) apply the same method of difference in temperature signals between forehead and nose-tip, identified by their HOG detector. Wesley et al. (2010) produce a mean of all collected temperature values in the tracked region of interest per measurement, obtaining a one-dimensional signal from the two-dimensional thermal data. Noise in the thermal data was reduced using a Fast Fourier Transformation-based method.

Anzengruber and Riener (2012) utilize an estimation-maximization algorithm to compute a Gaussian Mixture Model to identify regions of the face with the highest temperature. By calculating a mean, these values are then normalized by subtracting the starting temperature of the regions identified, thus determining the change in temperature of a facial region during a testing configuration. Pavlidis et al. (2018), and Panagopoulos and Pavlidis (2019) determine the amount of perspiration in the perinasal area by performing a contour-based black top-hat transformation which generates an image of areas of perspiration on a black background, thus enabling the calculation of the amount of perspiration as the energy in the image generated by the colored spots. They utilize the previously described method of Shastri et al. (2012).

Lastly, Wu et al. (2018) utilize the Supervised Descent Method by Xiong and De la Torre (2013) to produce a point-cloud of facial features and calculate 3D coordinates for each facial feature through vector calculation, thus determining the head position and orientation in three-dimensional space.

3.4. Summary appraisal

The evidence base exhibits substantial quality heterogeneity. Two studies (Pavlidis et al., 2018; Panagopoulos and Pavlidis, 2019)—both from the same research group—demonstrate methodological rigor approaching standards expected for applied ergonomics research. Five studies (Or and Duffy, 2007; Wesley et al., 2010; Kim et al., 2011; Jeong et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2019) exhibit moderate quality with identifiable

Figure 3: The Forest Plot shows the Standardized Mean-Difference (SMD) and the Confidence Intervals (CI) of the studies taken into consideration. The last line shows the size, with its CI, of the Random-Effects model. The Forest Plot also includes yellow “diamonds” for each study. These are the predicted effect sizes computed from the meta-regression model. The column *Setting* indicates where the study was conducted (in situ or ex situ), the *ROIs* where the thermophysiological data was extracted (forehead, nose tip, and perinasal). In column *Conditions*, C.D. stands for Cognitive Distraction, U.E. for Unexpected Event, and S.D. for Sensorimotor Distraction. To understand the output analysis, the SMD value is interpreted similarly to the effect size (*d*) defined as: *d* (0.01) = very small, *d* (0.2) = small, *d* (0.5) = medium, *d* (0.8) = large, *d* (1.2) = very large (Sawilowsky, 2009). Moreover, the CI indicates the precision with which we can calculate the SMD, facilitating the comparison between the studies.

limitations but adequate reporting for interpretation. The remaining studies exhibit substantial methodological limitations—very small samples, unreported specifications, unclear procedures—that constrain confidence in their findings. Notably, the four studies contributing to the meta-analysis represent the higher-quality subset of the evidence base. This partial self-selection mitigates (but does not eliminate) concerns about quality-driven bias in the quantitative synthesis. However, the concentration of high-quality evidence within a single research group (Pavlidis and colleagues) raises concerns about generalizability and independence that must inform interpretation.

4. Results of the Meta-Analysis

To determine the validity of the thermal camera as a tool for assessing cognitive load, we conducted a meta-analysis. We were interested in whether the null hypothesis of no effect could be rejected. From the 13 studies that we analyzed in-depth, four were suitable to be coded using the Population, Intervention, Comparison group, Outcomes, Time frame, Setting (PICOTS) framework (Riva et al., 2012). However, despite the limited amount of records available, we extracted 15 data points containing Standardized Mean-Difference (SMD) and Confidence Intervals (CI). Using this data, we ran a Random-Effects analysis using the R *METAFOR* package⁵ (Viechtbauer, 2010), carried out moderator and Meta-Regression analyses, and created Forest and Funnel plots (Figure 3 and Figure 4). We used a Random-Effects model since it does not assume that the estimated effects arise from a single homogeneous population; instead, that the true effect sizes differ between each study.

⁵<https://metafor-project.org/doku.php>

Figure 4: (a) The Funnel Plot of the Random-Effects analysis without explanatory variables, and (b) the Funnel Plot with explanatory variables (i.e., study setting, RoIs, and conditions). In (a), the data points are expected to lie in a confidence triangle 95% of the time. However, this is not the case; an excessive amount of points are outside the interval due to heterogeneity. In (b), the Funnel Plot of the meta-regression model is shown. Herewith, we see that the plot is symmetrical in the vertical axis around the meta-analytic compounded effect size estimate, suggesting that the moderators (i.e., study setting, RoIs, and conditions) do explain the differences between the studies; however, there is some excess of variance (> 5%).

The Omnibus test of the model coefficients shows to be significant ($Q = 32.96$, $DF = 1$, $p < .001$). Also, the test of Residual Heterogeneity shows to be significant ($Q = 248.46$, $DF = 14$, $p < .001$). The significance of both tests indicates a rejection of the null hypothesis of no effect and the hypothesis of homogeneity. The prior implies that the model (without explanatory variables such as study setting, the RoIs, and conditions) is significant. The latter implies that thermophysiological results differed across studies (heterogeneity of the effect sizes). To explain the excess of variance among the studies, we carried out a meta-regression that includes factors as RoIs where the thermophysiological data was extracted (e.g., forehead, nose tip, and perinasal region), the study setting—i.e., if the study was carried out in-situ (laboratory via driving simulator) or ex-situ (real environment). Moreover, we included study design factors as a type of distraction added to the condition (e.g., cognitive or sensorimotor distraction). Despite the specification cited, the Omnibus test of the model coefficients shows to be significant ($Q = 121.26$, $DF = 6$, $p < .001$), indicating two coefficients to be non-significant: *Drive + Sensorimotor Distraction* and *In-situ setting* (Table 3). The test of Residual Heterogeneity also shows to be significant ($Q = 34.42$, $DF = 8$, $p < .001$). The test indicates that although the moderators explain the differences between the studies, there is an unexplained excess of variance. Furthermore, we conducted an analysis to assess publication biases. The Rank correlation test for funnel plot asymmetry (Kendall's $\tau = 0.42$, $p = .03$) shows minor signs of asymmetry (Figure 4), indicating a bias of effect sizes included in our meta-analysis (Borenstein, 2009). Moreover, the Funnel Plot, visually, confirms an excess of heterogeneity due to the few data points (> 5%) that lie outside the confidence triangle.

Despite the variance of the observed effect sizes, the random-effects model (see the Forest Plot in Figure 3) estimates a positive aggregated effect for detecting cognitive load using thermal cameras, $SMD = 1.29$, $p < .01$, 95% CI [0.85, 1.72]. Taken at face value, this corresponds to a large standardized mean difference.

However, we emphasise that this estimate should be interpreted as *exploratory* rather than confirmatory evidence. First, only four studies (15 data points) could be included, due to incomplete reporting or insufficient diagnostic detail in the remaining records. Second, both the residual heterogeneity and the funnel-plot asymmetry indicate that the true effects likely vary substantially across studies and that some

	Estimate	SE	z	p	95% C. I.	
					Lower	Upper
Intercept	0.822	0.343	2.400	0.016	0.151	1.493
Setting (In situ)	-0.690	0.363	-1.899	0.058	-1.403	0.022
ROIs (Nose Tip)	1.764	0.212	8.310	< .001	1.348	2.180
ROIs (Perinasal)	1.191	0.426	2.798	0.005	0.357	2.025
Condition(s) (Drive + C.D.)	0.618	0.238	2.598	0.009	0.152	1.085
Condition(s) (Drive + U.E.)	-1.443	0.269	-5.354	< .001	-1.971	-0.915
Condition(s) (Drive + S.D.)	1.026	0.621	1.654	0.098	-0.190	2.243

Table 3: The table shows the estimated coefficients (via Wald test) for the Random-Effects analysis, along with their significance. Here, next to the intercept, one coefficient for Setting (in situ), two for ROIs (Nose Tip and Perinasal), and three for Conditions: Drive + Cognitive Distraction (C.D.), Unexpected Event (U.E.), and Sensorimotor Distraction (S.D.). Note: SE stands for Standard Error.

335 degree of bias in the available evidence cannot be excluded. Under these conditions, the aggregated effect size cannot be treated as a stable population parameter but rather as a hypothesis-generating summary of a small and heterogeneous body of work.

In summary, the meta-analytic results are compatible with the idea that thermal cameras can capture changes associated with cognitive load in driving simulators, but they also make visible the methodological and reporting limitations that currently prevent strong conclusions and robust generalization.

340 5. Discussion

This systematic review and exploratory meta-analysis provide the first qualitative and quantitative synthesis of infrared thermal imaging for driver state assessment in simulator environments. The pooled effect size (SMD = 1.29, 95% CI [0.85, 1.73]) suggests that thermal measures are sensitive to experimental manipulations intended to induce cognitive load or distraction. However, the substantial heterogeneity 345 observed ($I^2 = 54.98\%$), the significant residual variance unexplained by methodological moderators, and the detected publication bias (Kendall’s $\tau = 0.42$, $p = .03$) collectively indicate that this estimate should not be interpreted as a stable population parameter suitable for informing design decisions.

We propose that this heterogeneity itself constitutes a substantive finding rather than merely a limitation to be acknowledged. The variability across studies reflects the current state of a research domain that has not 350 yet achieved methodological consolidation. Specifically, our synthesis reveals construct heterogeneity and processing heterogeneity.

In construct heterogeneity, the reviewed studies operationalize “cognitive load” through diverse manipulations—secondary arithmetic tasks, unexpected driving events, sensorimotor distractions—that may engage different cognitive and physiological systems. Following the ISO 10075 framework, these 355 manipulations likely produce different profiles of mental strain, yet they are treated as equivalent instances of a unitary construct. The absence of standardized workload induction protocols makes it unclear whether observed temperature changes reflect task-specific cognitive demands, generalized sympathetic arousal, or some combination thereof.

When it comes to processing heterogeneity, the signal extraction pipelines—from manual RoI delineation 360 to HOG-based automatic detection, from simple temperature differencing to perinasal perspiration energy computation—introduce additional variance that confounds comparison across studies. The absence of shared processing protocols or benchmark datasets precludes assessment of which approaches optimize sensitivity and specificity.

The narrative quality assessment reinforces this interpretation. Methodological rigor varies substantially across studies, with nearly half the evidence base exhibiting limitations severe enough to constrain confidence in findings—small or single-participant samples, unreported camera specifications, unclear processing pipelines, inadequate confound control. The higher-quality studies cluster within a single research program (Pavlidis and colleagues), raising questions about whether observed effects generalize beyond the specific methodological configurations employed by that group. This quality distribution is characteristic of an emerging research domain prior to methodological consolidation, where pioneering groups establish approaches that have not yet been independently replicated or systematically compared.

This pattern of heterogeneity is characteristic of an immature measurement paradigm—one in which fundamental questions about what is being measured, how it should be measured, and under what conditions measurements are valid remain unresolved. The exploratory meta-analysis thus functions as a diagnostic instrument, revealing the methodological fragmentation that must be addressed before thermal imaging can be considered a validated tool for applied ergonomics.

5.1. Implications for Ergonomic Design Processes

Despite these limitations, the synthesized evidence permits preliminary assessment of how thermal imaging might be integrated into ergonomic design workflows. We address this question at three levels: evaluation contexts, decision criteria, and practical constraints.

5.1.1. Evaluation Contexts for Thermal Imaging

Based on the reviewed evidence, we identify three potential roles for thermal imaging within ergonomic evaluation processes: (a) summative evaluation in controlled settings, (b) formative evaluation during iterative design, and (c) continuous monitoring in operational contexts.

Summative evaluation in controlled settings. The strongest current evidence supports thermal imaging as a complementary measure in laboratory-based interface evaluations. In contexts where established measures (NASA-TLX, performance metrics, ECG/GSR) are already deployed, thermal indices can provide converging evidence of sympathetic arousal without additional participant burden. The reviewed studies consistently report correlations between thermal changes and both subjective workload reports and other physiological measures, supporting convergent validity within controlled environments.

Formative evaluation during iterative design. Thermal imaging may support rapid, low-burden assessment during early design iterations where full physiological instrumentation would be impractical. The contactless nature of the measurement permits evaluation of multiple design alternatives without repeated sensor attachment, potentially accelerating design cycles. However, the temporal dynamics of thermal responses—with reported delays of 30–120 seconds between workload onset and measurable temperature change (Altschaffel et al., 2014)—may limit utility for detecting transient workload peaks associated with specific interface interactions.

Continuous monitoring in operational contexts. The most demanding application, real-time driver state monitoring for adaptive interface intervention, remains inadequately validated. Only two studies (Panagopoulos and Pavlidis, 2019; Pavlidis et al., 2018) specifically address real-time detection, and both rely on perinasal perspiration indices rather than temperature per se. The ecological validity constraints identified in this review (environmental confounds, motion artifacts, occlusion) represent substantial barriers to operational deployment that have not been systematically addressed.

5.1.2. Decision Criteria When Considering Thermal Imaging

405 We propose a preliminary decision framework for ergonomics practitioners evaluating whether thermal imaging is appropriate for a specific assessment context. Thermal imaging may offer advantages over established methods when:

Criterion 1: Contact-based instrumentation is contraindicated. When electrode attachment would interfere with naturalistic behavior, restrict movement required for task performance, or introduce participant discomfort that confounds measurement, contactless thermal imaging offers a methodological alternative. This criterion 410 is most clearly satisfied in studies requiring unconstrained head and facial movement or extended monitoring periods where sensor adhesion degrades.

Criterion 2: Arousal-level assessment is sufficient. Based on the theoretical positioning developed in this review, thermal imaging appears to index sympathetic arousal rather than task-specific cognitive workload. 415 When the assessment question concerns overall strain level—for example, comparing interface alternatives expected to differ in general demandingness—thermal indices may provide useful information. When the question requires differentiation among specific workload components (perceptual, cognitive, motor; following Wickens' Multiple Resource Theory), thermal imaging alone is unlikely to provide adequate diagnostic resolution.

420 *Criterion 3: Environmental conditions are controlled.* The reviewed studies were conducted exclusively in simulator environments with controlled ambient temperature and lighting. Real-world deployment introduces confounds (solar radiation, HVAC fluctuations, seasonal variation) that directly affect facial temperature independent of cognitive state. Until calibration methods for these environmental factors are validated, thermal imaging should be considered primarily a laboratory technique.

425 *Criterion 4: Temporal resolution requirements are modest.* The thermal response latency documented in the literature (tens of seconds to minutes) precludes detection of rapid workload fluctuations. Applications requiring identification of momentary demand peaks, such as workload assessment during specific interface interactions or event-related designs, may be poorly served by thermal measures.

5.1.3. Practical Constraints with Human-Centered Design Workflows

430 For practitioners seeking to incorporate thermal imaging into established design processes, we offer the following operational guidance:

Within ISO 9241-210 (2019) human-centered design cycles. Thermal imaging is most appropriately positioned at the evaluation phase rather than requirements gathering or design phases. The measure provides summative evidence of strain associated with design alternatives but does not directly inform what aspects of design 435 should be modified. Integration with task analysis and heuristic evaluation methods is necessary to connect thermal findings to actionable design recommendations.

Multi-measure assessment protocols. Given the construct limitations identified in this review, thermal imaging should not serve as a sole workload measure. We recommend deployment alongside: (a) at least one subjective measure (NASA-TLX or domain-specific instrument) to capture the multidimensional workload experience; 440 (b) task performance metrics to index behavioral consequences; and (c) where feasible, at least one additional physiological measure (HRV, pupillometry) to triangulate arousal assessment. This multi-method approach

permits assessment of convergent validity within each study and guards against over-interpretation of thermal findings.

Threshold determination. The current evidence base does not support specification of thermal thresholds for design decisions (e.g., “temperature decrease exceeding X°C indicates unacceptable workload”). Effect sizes in the reviewed studies reflect group-level comparisons under controlled manipulations; individual-level classification accuracy—sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value—has not been systematically reported. Until diagnostic performance metrics are established, thermal imaging should inform relative comparisons (Alternative A vs. Alternative B) rather than absolute judgments (workload is/is not acceptable).

6. Future Work

The research agenda that follows derives directly from the design space analysis. Each priority addresses a methodological gap identified through systematic mapping of current approaches: where the design space reveals unexplored configurations or unresolved comparisons, we articulate corresponding research needs. This approach ensures that the agenda targets genuinely open questions rather than reiterating generic recommendations for “more research.”

Priority 1: Standardization of measurement protocols. The field requires convergence on: (a) a minimal set of validated ROIs with documented psychophysiological rationale; (b) standardized signal processing pipelines with openly shared implementation code; (c) benchmark datasets enabling comparison of alternative approaches; and (d) reporting guidelines specifying minimum methodological detail for publication.

Priority 2: Diagnostic performance characterization. Moving beyond group-level effect sizes, research should establish individual-level classification accuracy. What sensitivity and specificity can thermal imaging achieve for detecting elevated workload states? How do these metrics compare to established alternatives? What is the rate of false positives under varying environmental conditions?

Priority 3: Construct validation studies. Systematic investigation is needed of which workload components thermal indices track. Factorial designs crossing different demand types (perceptual, cognitive, motor) with thermal measurement could clarify the construct validity boundaries of the approach.

Priority 4: Ecological validity investigation. Controlled studies systematically varying environmental parameters (ambient temperature, humidity, lighting) are needed to characterize confound magnitude and develop calibration approaches. On-road studies with appropriate safety protocols could assess whether simulator-based findings generalize to naturalistic driving.

Priority 5: Integration with driver monitoring systems. For applied ergonomics applications in automotive contexts, research should address how thermal imaging might complement existing driver monitoring modalities (gaze tracking, steering behavior, lane position) within multi-sensor fusion architectures. The unique contribution of thermal data relative to more mature modalities remains to be established.

Priority 6: Temporal dynamics characterization. The latency and time constants of thermal responses require systematic investigation to determine which applications are temporally feasible. Can signal processing approaches (e.g., rate-of-change indices) improve temporal resolution? What workload dynamics are and are not detectable with thermal measures?

480 *Priority 7: Individual differences and calibration.* Participant factors (body composition, metabolic rate, acclimatization, baseline sympathetic tone) likely moderate thermal responses. Research should establish whether individual calibration is necessary and, if so, what calibration protocols are minimally sufficient.

7. Limitations

Several limitations of this review warrant acknowledgment beyond those already discussed:

485 *Search scope.* The restriction to four databases (IEEE Xplore, SAGE, Springer, Elsevier) may have excluded relevant studies indexed elsewhere. The keyword strategy, while systematic, may have missed studies using alternative terminology.

Quality assessment. We employed narrative rather than quantitative quality assessment, foregoing numerical scores in favor of domain-specific characterization. This approach provides transparency about specific methodological concerns but does not permit quality-weighted meta-analysis or formal sensitivity analyses.

Statistical dependencies. The meta-analytic model treated multiple effect sizes from the same study as independent observations. More sophisticated approaches (multilevel modeling, robust variance estimation) would be appropriate for future syntheses as the evidence base grows.

495 *Publication bias.* The significant funnel plot asymmetry suggests the pooled effect may be inflated. Bias-corrected estimates were not computed but would likely yield more conservative conclusions.

Generalizability. The restriction to simulator studies, while necessary for methodological comparability, limits generalization to real-world automotive applications.

Data Availability Statement

500 The dataset supporting this systematic review and meta-analysis, including extracted effect sizes and moderator classifications, is available in the Open Science Framework repository ⁶. The complete analysis is provided as supplementary material, enabling full reproducibility of the random-effects model, meta-regression, and publication bias analyses. The systematic review was conducted following PRISMA guidelines; the completed checklist is available as supplementary material.

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⁶https://osf.io/y5he4/overview?view_only=a81dca8874eb40ec9b94ac60418fd115

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